

Performance and Job Satisfaction: Empirical Study on Transformational Leadership, Organizational Commitment, and Employee Motivation in Jember

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Abstract:-

Backgrounds:The aims of study were to determine transformational leadership on job satisfaction; organizational commitment to job satisfaction; motivation and job satisfaction; transformational leadership on performance; organizational commitment to employee performance; motivation on employee performance and job satisfaction on employee performance. This study uses explanatory research with path analysis. The number of respondents were 45 employees.

Keywords:- transformational leadership, organizational commitment, motivation, job satisfaction and employee performance.

I. INTRODUCTION

Human resources are one of the most important organizational resources and become the main driver of all organizational activities, so there needs to be a serious attention to the management of human resources. Without human resources, a company cannot function and only with human resources who have a high level of professionalism will a company achieve high productivity (Simamora, 2006:4). Human resources have an important role in organizations and companies.

The level of success of the company can be seen from the company's performance in managing its resources. According to Sedarmayanti (2014: 147) performance as result of work that can be achieved by a group or person in organization with their respective and responsibilities to achieve goals in organization with moral ethics.

Transformational leadership style is a leadership style that is believed to be able to balance the human mindset in the current era of globalization. As according to Asrar-ul-Haq and Kuchinke (2016:54–64), “A transformational leader usually leads its employees by providing them a clear vision”. This means that transformational leadership can effect employee providing to motivate employees to work in order to achieve a goal in the organization.

Comitmen in organization include all element to loyalty for organization involment in work and identification of value and goals organization. Motivation driven force that causes a member organization to be willing to mobilize abilities in the form of expertise or skills, energy and time to activiactivities that are their responsibility and fulfill their obligations(Siagian, 2007).

Wibowo (2011: 501) explained job satisfaction a degree of positive or negative feeling about task, worplace and relationship between workers. Kreiter and Kinicki (2001:271) explained that job satisfaction was effective for aspect of work.

II. METHOD

The design oh this research was *explanatory research* or hypothesis in order to strengthen the theory. This study used two types of data sources, namely primary data and secondary data. Primary data questionnaires. While secondary data is data obtained indirectly from the object under study (Sumarsono, 2004:69). Secondary data sources were obtained from journals, books, previous research, internet, and published thesis relating to the variables of transformational leadership, commitment of organizational and motivation on employee performance through job satisfaction. The analytical tools used to solve the existing problems are: path analysis (*Path Analysis*).

III. RESULT

A. Hypothesis testing

To test the significance level of the established hypothesis, this study uses hypothesis testing, namely the t-test on $\alpha = 0.05$ or p-value < 0.05 as the significance level of the direct influence of the independent variables on the dependent variable.

• H1: The Effect of Transformational Leadership on Job Satisfaction

Based on the table (Path Analysis test) testing the transformational leadership variable on job satisfaction obtained a beta value (β) of 0.302, t count = 3.754 and obtained the value of t table = 2.014 so t count > t table so that H_0 is rejected. Thus it can be concluded that transformational leadership has a significant effect on employee job satisfaction (H_{a1} is accepted).

• H2: he Effect of Organizational Commitment on Job Satisfaction

Based on the table (Path Analysis test) testing the organizational commitment variable on job satisfaction obtained a beta value (β) of 0.634, t count = 8.053 and obtained the value of t table = 2.014 so t count > t table so that H_0 is rejected. Thus, it can be concluded that organizational commitment has a significant effect on employee job satisfaction (H_{a2} is accepted).

• H3: The Effect of Motivation on Job Satisfaction

Based on the table (Path Analysis test) testing the motivation variable on job satisfaction obtained a beta

value (β) of 0.145, t count = 2,908 and obtained the value of t table = 2.014 so t count > t table so that H_0 is rejected. Thus it can be concluded that motivation has a significant effect on employee job satisfaction (H_{a3} accepted).

• H4: The Effect of Transformational Leadership on Employee Performance

Based on the table (Path Analysis test) testing the transformational leadership variable on employee performance obtained a beta value (β) of 0.280, t count = 2,748 and obtained the value of t table = 2.014 so t count > t table so that H_0 is rejected. Thus, it can be concluded that transformational leadership has a significant effect on employee performance (H_{a4} accepted).

• H5: The Effect of Organizational Commitment on Employee Performance

Hypothesis testing result that organizational commitment variable on employee performance obtained a beta value (β) of 0.483, t count = 3,483 and obtained the value of t table = 2.014 so H_0 is rejected. It means organizational commitment had a significant effect on employee performance (H_{a5} accepted).

• H6: The Effect of Motivation on Employee Performance

The testing result showed motivation variable on employee performance, the beta (β) value is 0.208, t count = 3,475 and obtained the value of t table = 2.014 so H_0 was rejected. It means motivation had a significant effect on employee performance (H_{a6} is accepted).

• H7: The Effect of Job Satisfaction on Employee Performance

The testing result that the satisfaction variable on employee performance obtained a beta value (β) of 0.422, t count = 2,467 and obtained the value of t table = 2.014 so t count > t table so that H_0 is rejected. Thus it can be concluded that job satisfaction has a significant effect on employee performance (H_{a7} accepted).

B. Path Analysis

This section describes the significance of each path in the model using path analysis. Each path tested shows the direct and indirect effect of transformational leadership, organizational commitment, and motivation on employee performance through job satisfaction. The path analysis model is presented in Figure 1 below:

Fig. 1: Path Analysis Results

IV. DISCUSSION

A. The Effect of Transformational Leadership on Job Satisfaction

Based on the results of the study, Transformational Leadership has an influence on employee job satisfaction because it has a significance value that is smaller than the specified significance value of 5% or (0.05), it can be concluded that the Transformational Leadership variable is proven to significantly affect employee job satisfaction. This shows that the Transformational Leadership that is applied is in accordance with the expectations of employees so as to form an employee job satisfaction.

The first hypothesis in this study, which states that Transformational Leadership has an effect on employee job satisfaction, is accepted. It can be concluded that Transformational Leadership has an influence on employee job satisfaction, meaning that the role of Transformational Leadership on employee job satisfaction is significant, if the Transformational Leadership of employees is improved it will also increase employee job satisfaction.

B. The Effect of Organizational Commitment on Job Satisfaction

Based on the results of the study, Organizational Commitment has an influence on employee job satisfaction because it has a significance value that is smaller than the specified significance value of 5% or (0.05), it can be concluded that the organizational commitment variable is proven to significantly affect employee job satisfaction. This shows that the Organizational Commitment is implemented in accordance with the expectations of employees so as to form an employee job satisfaction.

The second hypothesis in this study, which states that organizational commitment has an effect on employee job satisfaction, is accepted. Conclusions can be drawn Organizational Commitment have an influence on employee job satisfaction means the role of Organizational Commitment to employee job satisfaction is significant, if Employee Organizational Commitment is increased, it will also increase employee job satisfaction.

C. The Effect of Motivation on Job Satisfaction

Motivation has an influence on employee job satisfaction because it has a significance value that is smaller than the specified significance value of 5% or (0.05), it can be concluded that the motivation variable is proven to significantly affect employee job satisfaction. This shows that the applied motivation is in accordance with employee expectations so as to form an employee job satisfaction.

Based on the results of this study, so the third hypothesis which states that motivation has an effect on employee job satisfaction, is accepted. Conclusions can be drawn Motivation had effect on employee job satisfaction means the role of Motivation to job satisfaction was significant, if Employee motivation is increased, it will also increase job satisfaction.

D. *The Effect of Transformational Leadership on Employee Performance*

Transformational Leadership has an influence on Employee Performance because it has a significance value that is under 0.05, it can be concluded that the Transformational Leadership variable is proven to significantly affect Employee Performance. This shows that Transformational Leadership is implemented in accordance with employee expectations so as to form an Employee Performance.

The fourth hypothesis said Transformational Leadership had an effect on Employee performance, accepted. If the employee's Transformational Leadership is improved, it will also increase Employee performance.

E. *The Effect of Organizational Commitment on Employee Performance*

Organizational Commitment had significant effect on Employee Performance because it has a significance value that is under 0.05. It Organizational Commitment variable is proven to significantly affect Employee Performance. This shows that the Organizational Commitment is implemented in accordance with the expectations of employees so as to form an Employee Performance.

Based on the results of this study, so the fifth hypothesis in this study states that Organizational Commitment affects Employee Performance, is accepted. Conclusions can be drawn Organizational Commitment had effect on Employee performance increased, it will also increase Employee performance.

F. *The Effect of Motivation on Employee Performance*

Motivation has a significant effect on employee performance. The motivation variable increased employee performance. This shows that the applied motivation is in accordance with employee expectations so as to form an employee performance.

The sixth hypothesis in this study, which states that motivation affects employee performance, is accepted. Conclusions can be drawn Motivation have an influence on Employee performance. If Employee motivation is increased, it will also increase Employee performance.

G. *The Effect of Job Satisfaction on Employee Performance*

Based on the results of the study, job satisfaction has an influence on employee performance because it has a significance value that is under 0.05. The job satisfaction is proven to significantly affect employee performance. This shows that Job Satisfaction is applied in accordance with employee expectations so as to form an Employee Performance.

Based on the results of this study, so the seventh hypothesis in this study states that job satisfaction affects employee performance, is accepted. Conclusions can be drawn Job satisfaction have an influence on Employee performance. If Employee Job Satisfaction is increased, it will also increase Employee performance.

V. CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

A. *Conclusion*

- Leadership transformational influence on job satisfaction
- Organizational Commitment influence a job satisfaction
- Motivation influence on job satisfaction Employee
- Transformational leadership is significant to employee performance
- Organizational Commitment influence on employee performance
- Motivation influence on employee performance
- Job Satisfaction influence on employee performance

B. *Suggestion*

- Transformational leadership improved by providing employee training
- Organizational Commitment to evaluate jointly to unite goals.
- Motivation can be improved by building emotional relationships with other employees to be able to support each other.
- Job satisfaction can be increased by evaluating and finding joint solutions to work results so that they can be maximized.

REFERENCES

- [1.] Asrar-ul-Haq and Kuchinke. 2016. Impact Of Leadership Styles on Employees' Attitude Towards Their Leader and Performance: Empirical Evidence from Pakistani Banks. *Future Business Journal* 2, h:54–64
- [2.] Kreitner, K. dan A. Kinicki. 2014. *Perilaku Organisasional*. Edisi 9. Jakarta: Salemba Empat, h:165
- [3.] Malayu S.P Hasibuan. 2003. *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia*. Jakarta: Bumi Aksara.
- [4.] Richard M. Steers dalam Kuntjoro. 2002. *Employee Training and Development*, International Edition. McGraw –Hill, Inc.
- [5.] Sarwono, Jonathan, dan Herlina Budiono. 2006. *Statistik Terapan: Aplikasi Untuk Riset Skripsi, Thesis, dan Disertasi (Menggunakan SPSS, AMOS, dan Excel)*. Jakarta: PT Elex Media Komputindo.
- [6.] Siagian P. Sondang. 2004. *Teori motivasi dan Aplikasinya*. Edisi 3. Jakarta: PT. Rineka Cipta.
- [7.] Simamora. 2006. *Panduan Riset Perilaku Konsumen*. Jakarta :Gramedia.
- [8.] Sumarsono, Sonny. 2004. *Metode Riset Sumber Daya Manusia*. Jember: Graham Ilmu.
- [9.] Wibowo. 2011. *Manajemen Kinerja*. Jakarta: Raja Grafindo Persada